

USEFULNESS OF C-REACTIVE PROTEIN AS AN INDICATOR OF NEONATAL SEPSIS

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Abstract

Objectives: To determine diagnostic usefulness of CRP to diagnose “neonatal sepsis (NS)”.

Study design: Validation study.

Place and duration of Study: “CMH, Rawalpindi from 15 Oct 2023 to 15 March 2024”.

Methodology: 107 neonates fulfilling the inclusion criteria were included in the study. Two separate blood sample were taken. One sample was sent for CRP levels and other sample was sent for blood culture to make definitive diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis”. 2x2 table was drawn for calculating “sensitivity”, “specificity”, PPV, NPV and accuracy. Data was analyzed by SPSS 20.00.

Results: Mean gestational age at birth of 39.28 ± 1.57 weeks. There were 62 (57.94%) male and 45 (42.06%) female neonates. Mean birth weight of the neonates was 3.06 ± 0.35 kg. Frequency of neonates who were found to have “CRP > 5mg/dl” was 86 (80.37%) while total number of neonates who were found to have positive blood culture was 85 (79.44%). “Sensitivity”, “specificity”, PPV, NPV and accuracy of CRP to diagnose NS was 89.42%, 54.55%, 88.37%, 57.14% and 82.24%, respectively.

Conclusion: CRP is a highly useful test with high diagnostic accuracy to identify a case of “neonatal sepsis”.

INTRODUCTION

Approximately four million infants perish annually during the process of delivery, a remarkable figure that necessitates substantial endeavors from the healthcare system and advocates striving to reduce and manage it. Low-income nations account for majority of newborn mortality accounting for approximately two and a half million neonatal deaths occurring every year in countries with striving economies. ¹ In low-

income nations such as Pakistan, there is a notable prevalence of infant mortality, with roughly 18% of cases occurring within the initial month of life as a result of neonatal sepsis. ² Neonatal sepsis is diagnosed when a positive blood culture is obtained within the first twenty-eight days after birth. The defining characteristics of this condition include inflammation and a failure of the circulatory system, which are

evident in clinical manifestations such as fever, drowsiness reluctance to feeding, and inadequate perfusion. It can be categorized into two stages: early (occurring within the first 72 hours of life of a neonate) and late (occurring beyond 72 hours after the birth).^{3,4}

Various organisms, such as *Acinetobacter*, *Klebsiella species*, *Salmonella paratyphi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Serratia species*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Group A *Streptococcus*, and *Pseudomonas species*, are commonly identified as the causative agents in newborns with “neonatal sepsis (NS)”.^{5,6} Furthermore, there exists a significant apprehension regarding the escalating resistance of diverse antibiotics employed in the management of “neonatal sepsis (NS)”.⁷ When it comes to evaluation for “neonatal sepsis (NS)”, in order to make a definitive diagnosis, best test that can be performed is blood culture that not only confirms the diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” but also provide information regarding the culprit organism along with its drug susceptibility.⁸ Since blood culture reports take time and the treatment of sepsis cannot be delayed while waiting for diagnosis, a rapid indicator that can effectively diagnose “neonatal sepsis (NS)” is a necessity. In this instance, several blood test have been reported in literature that are quick to perform and can serve as useful investigation to make quicker diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” including the serum levels of “interleukin-6 (IL-6)”, “procalcitonin (PCT)”, “endoscan (ESM-1)” and “interleukin-8 (IL-8)”.⁹ However, these not only are expensive but also scarcely available tests particularly in the health care facilities located in the periphery. Alternatively, “C-reactive protein (CRP)” has been hypothesized to be useful in this regard which not only is quick and cheap but also is readily available. Present study focused on determining the diagnostic usefulness of this cheap, quick and readily available blood test, i.e., “C-reactive protein (CRP)” to effectively diagnose cases of “neonatal sepsis (NS)”.

METHODOLOGY

This comparative validation study was conducted at “CMH, Rawalpindi from 15 Oct 2023 to 15 March 2024” after taking approval from

institutional ethical review board (IERB #: 636). Appropriate sample size was calculated using “WHO sample size calculator for single population proportions with specified absolute precision” using following formula:

$$n = \frac{z_{1-\alpha/2}^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

For calculations, following assumptions were used; “confidence level of significance of 95%”, “absolute precision of 8%” and “anticipated sensitivity of CRP in making diagnosis of neonatal sepsis” of 76.92%.¹⁰ This gave a sample size of 107.

Inclusion criteria: All neonates aged ≤ 28 days, both male and female gender, who were admitted at the NICU with clinical suspicion of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” were included in this study.

Exclusion criteria: Infants aged more than 28 days, who had “birth asphyxia”, birth weight of less than 1500g, age of gestation at birth less than 37 weeks and neonates who were already put on a drug regimen containing antibiotics were excluded from the study.

Patients were selected by using “non-probability consecutive sampling technique”. High clinical suspicion of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” was considered if a neonate presented with ≥ 4 typical clinical features of NS including fever, lethargy, and reluctance to take feed, jaundice, abdominal distension, vomiting, increased heart rate and respiratory distress.¹¹ Once selected, all the baseline characteristics including gestational age (in weeks), gender and birth weight (in kg) were documented. After this, a 2ml blood sample was drawn from the neonate by the expert staff nurse which was placed in serum vial and was sent to the in-hospital laboratory for assessment of CRP levels. CRP levels $> 5\text{mg/dl}$ were considered indicative of “neonatal sepsis (NS)”.¹⁰ A second 10ml blood sample was taken by another staff nurse under strict aseptic conditions which, after placement in the aerobic and anaerobic culture vials (containing 5ml blood each), was sent to in-hospital laboratory to make definitive diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)”. Based on the results of

both tests, 2x2 contingency table were drawn which were then used to calculate “sensitivity (SN)”, “specificity (SP)”, “positive predictive value (PPV)”, “negative predictive value (NPV)” and accuracy of CRP in making diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” while keeping blood culture and sensitivity as reference standard.

“Data was analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.00. Numeric variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Categorical variables were represented by using percentage and frequency. Based on standard formulas, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and accuracy of CRP were calculated”.

RESULTS

Present study included 107 patients with the mean gestational age at birth of 39.28 ± 1.57 weeks. There were 62 (57.94%) male and 45 (42.06%) female neonates. Mean birth weight of the neonates was 3.06 ± 0.35 kg. Frequency of neonates who were found to have “CRP > 5mg/dl” was 86 (80.37%) while total number of neonates who were found to have positive blood culture was 85 (79.44%). Neonates who had both “CRP > 5mg/dl” as well as positive blood culture were 76 (71.03%) [TP]. Neonates who had “CRP > 5mg/dl” but had negative blood culture were 10 (9.35%) [FP]. Similarly, neonates who had “CRP ≤ 5mg/dl” but had positive blood culture were 9 (8.41%) [FN]. Neonates who had “CRP ≤ 5mg/dl” as well as negative blood culture were 12 (11.21%) [TN]. Based on these following 2x2 contingency table for CRP was drawn (table I):

Table I: 2x2 Contingency table of CRP for TP, TN, FP and FN (n = 107)

	Positive blood culture	Negative blood culture
CRP > 5mg/dl	76 (TP)	10 (FP)
CRP ≤ 5mg/dl	9 (FN)	12 (TN)

Based on the formulas mentioned above we found that sensitivity (SN), specificity (SP), positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV) and accuracy of CRP to make diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” while keeping blood culture and sensitivity as reference standard are given below in table II:

Table II: Sensitivity, Specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy of CRP in diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” while keeping blood culture and sensitivity as reference standard (n = 107)

	CRP
Sensitivity “[TP/TP+FN x 100]”	89.42%
Specificity “[TN/FP+TN x 100]”	54.55%
PPV “[TP/TP+FP x 100]”	88.37%
NPV “[TN/FN+TN x 100]”	57.14%
Accuracy “[TP+TN/TP+TN+FP+FN x 100]”	82.24%

DISCUSSION

Neonatal age is one of the most risk prone period in the life of a human being in which there is high propensity of developing a myriad of

morbidities particularly the infections that can threaten the life of a newborn due to immaturity of the immune system.^{12, 13} For this purpose, it is of utmost importance that the presence of

“neonatal sepsis (NS)” can be detected as early as possible to reduce its associated risk of mortality for which gold standard diagnostic investigation for “neonatal sepsis” is blood culture and sensitivity.^{14, 15} Owing to time lapse between presentation and blood culture results, quicker alternative investigations that can potentially indicate presence of “neonatal sepsis” are essential. One such test is “C-reactive protein (CRP)” which has been reported to be useful indicator of sepsis in adults¹⁶ was the focus of present study.

In present study, a male predominance was observed in terms of occurrence of “neonatal sepsis”. Similar trend has been observed in multiple studies that have focused on various aspects of “neonatal sepsis”.^{17, 18} In present study, when CRP value was set at a threshold of > 5mg/dl, its accuracy to effectively diagnose “neonatal sepsis (NS)” was found to be at 82.24%. Compared to present study, Hisamuddin et al.¹⁰ reported the accuracy of CRP to detect presence of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” at 70.07% which was relatively less than what has been found in present study. In a study conducted by Younis et al.¹⁹, “sensitivity” and “specificity” of CRP to diagnose “neonatal sepsis (NS)” was found at 97.3% and 95.2%, respectively, which was much higher as compared to what has been found in present study. In another study conducted by Eschborn et al.²⁰, “sensitivity” and “specificity” of CRP in making diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” were reported at 66.4% and 91.3%, respectively. This trend was opposite to what has been found in present study. Contrarily, one study found that “sensitivity” of CRP to diagnose “neonatal sepsis” was only 35.52% which compared to present study was much less, while the “specificity” reported was 58% which was comparable to present study.²¹

Findings of present study exhibit that CRP levels are highly useful indicator of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” and thus can effectively be used for early diagnosis of “neonatal sepsis”. Therefore, it is recommended that this useful diagnostic test should be used in conjunction of blood culture and sensitivity and if positive, appropriate

antibiotic therapy should be initiated promptly. Limitations of the study included limited sample size, inclusion of both types of NS as a single population and study limited to sample of a single center.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, CRP can be considered a highly useful indicator of “neonatal sepsis (NS)” with a diagnostic accuracy of CRP to diagnose “neonatal sepsis (NS)” of 82.24%.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS

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